

Effect of Smoke Drying Techniques on the Proximate and Mineral Composition of Macrobrachium vollenhovenii (African River Prawn)

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Abstract : This study was carried out to evaluate the nutritional composition of the African River Prawn (*Macrobrachium vollenhovenii*) in relation to Chokor (traditional) and Altona (improved traditional) drying techniques used in the preservation and processing of prawns by carrying out proximate composition analysis. The value obtained for the proximate analysis of Chokor and Altona smoke dried prawns were; Moisture (14.90% and 15.15%), Dry matter (85.10% and 84.85%), Protein (55.80% and 58.87%), Crude fat (1.95% and 1.98%), Crude fibre (21.40% and 13.11%), Carbohydrate (0.54% and 0.54%) and Ash (19.76% and 15.86%) respectively. The proximate mineral composition of Chokor and Altona smoke dried prawns were; Calcium (5.66% and 4.20%) and Phosphorus (9.22% and 6.34%) respectively. Result shows there was no loss of nutritional value with respect to Chokor and Altona drying techniques used in the processing of prawns

Keywords : Altona, Chokor, *Macrobrachium vollenhovenii*, Proximate Composition, Smoke drying.

Conference Title : ICEP 2014 : International Conference on Electronic Publications

Conference Location : journal city, WASET

Conference Dates : November 23-23, 2014